

THE IMPACT OF WORK RELATED STRESS AND JOB PERFORMANCE AMONG STAFF NURSE

Saira Mushtaque^{*1}, Munwar-Us-Salam², Rubina Parveen³, Fahmeeda Shar⁴, Huda Fatima⁵

^{*1,4,5}BSN Student, Begum Bilquees Sultana Institute of Nursing, People's University of Medical and Health Sciences for Women Nawabshah, SBA

²Associate Professor, Begum Bilquees Sultana Institute of Nursing, People's University of Medical and Health Sciences for Women Nawabshah, SBA

³Assistant Professor, Begum Bilquees Sultana Institute of Nursing, People's University of Medical and Health Sciences for Women Nawabshah, SBA

^{*1}sairabalochbaloch92@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18833264>

Keywords

Work related stress, job performance, staff nurse

Article History

Received: 29 December 2025

Accepted: 14 February 2026

Published: 28 February 2026

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Saira Mushtaque

Abstract

Background: Work Related stress is a major occupational concern in nursing and has been linked to reduced job performance, compromised patient safety, and workforce instability. Nurses working in critical care and high-acuity hospital units are particularly vulnerable due to heavy workloads, emotional demands, and time pressure.

Objective: To assess the level of work-related stress among nurses at Civil Hospital Nawabshah and examine its relationship with job performance.

Material Methods: A descriptive correlational design was employed. Data were collected from 187 staff nurses working in intensive care units, operating rooms, emergency departments, and other clinical wards using a Work-Related Stress Questionnaire and the Observation Checklist of Nurses' Performance. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze demographic variables, stress levels, and performance scores.

Results: The mean age of participants was 41.92 ± 9.96 years. Most respondents were male (69.5%), married (71.1%), and diploma-qualified (71.66%). Although nurses reported high job demands, including time pressure and physical and emotional workload, the majority (95.7%) demonstrated overall low work-related stress scores. Strong coworker and supervisory support were evident. However, role ambiguity and communication gaps were noted. Job-performance results showed that most nurses scored in the poor category (79.7%), particularly in therapeutic communication and patient education.

Conclusion: Despite relatively low overall stress levels, high job demands and organizational challenges appear to negatively influence important aspects of nursing performance. Strengthening organizational support, improving communication, and addressing workload issues are essential to enhancing nurse well-being and patient care quality.

INTRODUCTION

Nursing is an extremely delicate and demanding profession, Nurses are often exposed to situation

that can negatively affect their physical and mental health. They are responsible for caring for

the sick, handling emergencies, managing complex systems, dealing with dying patients and operating complicated equipment. Work related stress, also known as job stress, is commonly described as the feeling of work related frustration, distress, or tension. It usually develops due to many challenges nurses face the nurses. Stress is the result of several negative factor in the work environment. It causes changes in normal physical and psychological functioning leading to unhappiness, anxiety, tension, burnout and high turnover rate. In today's world nurses face many stressful working conditions while trying to meet the physical and psychological needs of patient .Therefore, maintaining good working condition is very important in every organization.The united nation has recognized stress as a major issue and labeled job related stress as the disease of the 20th century . It is very important to understand the factors that contribute to job stress and their impact on work performance. among nurses , job stress has multiple effects such as influencing patient safety ,the quality of care , job performance , nurses , health , patient satisfaction , and overall productivity. Therefore work related stress is considered an important topic in the healthcare sector because of its wide impact .Job stress is a serious concern due to its negative impact on workers' health and safety .It can lead to cardiovascular diseases , stomach problem, sleep disturbance, mental health issues , fatigue , and job dissatisfaction. As per bullying affects in role performance, causes psychological distress and mental burden and interrupt daily activities. Jamal (1984) indicated that stress happen because of an unsecured environment policies and incidents in an organization that causing poorer productivity and performance.

Stress had been identified as to the documental to the work output of employee and ought therefore to be kept at the barest minimum if performance is maximized. In recent years, stress has increased in all areas of life, particularly in

the workplace. Stress is defined as many discomfort by the individual that is stimulated by activity perceived as top intense and frequent, which exceed a person's coping capabilities and resources to manage.

Intensive care units, operation room, emergency department and high risk unit's deals with very critical and dangerous causes that require high level nursing care by staff nurse in such condition staff nurse more reliable to work related stress. Work related stress can result in a variety of challenges that divert nurses attention from their work to other situation and times ,will have a detrimental influence on the nurses level of performance and the efficiency with which the staff nurses can accomplish their job related roles and responsibilities.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study employed descriptive cross-sectional design to investigate the relationship between work related stress and job performance among staff nurses. The research was conducted in all general and surgical units at civil hospital Nawabshah. The study duration was 2 months from 17 November to 17 January, after obtaining approval from Institutional Review Board (IRB). The sample size was 187 calculated using Rao Soft software with a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error. A non-probability convenience sampling technique was used. Inclusion criteria were nurses working in ward, both genders and those who agreed to participate. Exclusion criteria were nurses who disagreed or were not working. Data were collected through structured questionnaire consisting three sections: Section A Sociodemographic information, Section B work related stress questionnaire and section C assessed job performance among staff nurses. Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 25, where frequencies ad percentages were calculated for categorical variables.

RESULTS

Figure 1: Age of Respondents

Figure 2: Gender of Respondents

Figure 3: Residence of Respondents

Figure 4: Education of Respondents

Figure 5: Year of Experience

Figure 6: Unit of Wards

Table 1: Work Related Stress

Questions	Absolutely agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Absolutely disagree
Can you rely on your colleagues for help when you face difficulties at work?	(167)89.3%	(18)9.6%	1(0.5%)	1(5%)	(2)1.1%
Do your co-worker share their knowledge and experience with you?	(132)70.6%	(51)27.3%	(2)1.1%	(1)5%	(1)5%
Do you feel emotionally supported by your colleagues?	(121)64.7%	(55)29.4%	(6)3.2%	(2)1.6%	(3)1.1%
Do you and your colleagues cooperate to develop creative ideas at work?	(77)41.2%	(89)47.6%	(18)9.6%	(7)3.7%	(4)2.1%
Do you have the freedom to decide how to carry out your job tasks?	(73)39.0%	(82)43.9%	(22)11.8%	(7)3.7%	(3)1.6%
Can you determine your own work schedule?	(72)38.5%	(72)38.5%	(29)15.5%	(7)3.7%	(4)2.1%
Are you able to use your own judgment when making decisions about your work?	(91)48.7%	(46)24.6%	(31)16.6%	(11)5.9%	(8)4.3%
Does your organization value and consider your opinions and suggestion?	(86)46.0%	(53)28.3%	(32)17.1%	(8)4.3%	(8)4.3%
Does your job require you to work very hard?	(98)52.4%	(42)22.5%	(29)15.5%	(10)5.3%	(8)4.3%
Does you often experience high time pressure in your job?	(142)75.9%	(40)21.4%	(4)2.1%	(4)2.1%	(1)5%
Does your work require sustained mental or emotional effort?	(104)55.6%	(75)40.1%	(7)3.7%	(1)5%	(2)1.1%
Are the physical and psychological demands of your job high?	(89)47.6%	(82)43.9%	(11)5.9%	(2)1.1%	(3)1.6%
Do you have clear goals and objective for your job?	(66)35.3%	(89)47.6%	(22)11.8%	2(1.1%)	(1)5%
Do you often feel uncertain about what tasks you are responsible for?	(60)32.1%	(81)43.3%	(34)18.2%	(7)3.7%	(5)2.7%
Are you unclear about the expectation of your role?	(77)41.2%	(57)30.5%	(37)19.8%	(9)4.8%	(7)3.7%
Do you lack sufficient information to carry out your job duties effectively?	(90)48.1%	(46)24.6%	(37)19.8%	(9)4.8%	(7)3.7%
Does your supervisor provide you with guidance and feedback when needed?	(97)51.9%	(40)21.4%	(35)18.7%	(8)4.3%	(7)3.7%
Does you feel supported by your supervisor in handling work challenges?	(92)49.2%	(44)23.5%	(28)15.0%	(13)7.0%	(10)5.3%
Does your supervisor value your contribution and efforts?	(103)55.1%	(40)21.4%	(30)16.0%	(9)4.8%	(5)2.7%

Table 2: Organize Nursing Care

Questions	Yes	No	Not Applicable
Does the nurse demonstrate the ability to organize nursing care effectively?	181(96.8%)	1(.5%)	2(1.1%)
Does the nurse provide clear guidance and direction to colleagues?	155(82.9%)	30(16.0%)	2(1.1%)
Does the nurse maintain professional behavior in stressful situation?	151(80.7%)	25(13.4%)	10(5.3%)
Does the nurse show respect for patient dignity and rights? Frequency Percent	123(65.8%)	54(28.9%)	9(4.8%)
Does the nurse provide reassurance during stressful procedures? Frequency Percent	116(62.0%)	66(35.3%)	5(2.7%)
Does the nurse use therapeutic communication techniques?	91(48.7%)	82(43.9%)	14(7.5%)
Does the nurse provide accurate information to patients?	97(51.9%)	71(38.0%)	18(9.6%)

Table 3: Work Related Stress Total

WLS total score	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 50%	179	95.7%
50-75%	8	4.7%
Total	187	100.0%

Table 4: Job Performance Total Score

JP total score	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 50%poor	149	79.7%
50-75 fair	38	20.3%
Total	187	100.0%

DISCUSSION

The present study identified that nurse's experienced considerable job demands, including time pressure, emotional exhaustion, and physical workload. Similar findings have been reported in recent studies, which emphasize that nursing is a highly demanding profession and that excessive workload is a primary source of work-related stress. High job demands have been consistently associated with psychological strain and reduced occupational well-being among nurses.

Despite high job demands, many nurses in the current study reported overall low perceived stress. This finding may be explained by the presence of supportive coworkers and supervisors. Recent evidence suggests that social support in the workplace plays a significant

protective role by reducing the negative impact of stressors on nurses' mental health. Supportive leadership and teamwork have been shown to buffer stress even in high-pressure clinical environments.

However, role ambiguity and lack of clear communication were reported by some participants. According to recent studies, unclear job roles and insufficient information significantly contribute to occupational stress and dissatisfaction among nurses. This suggests that organizational communication remains a critical area for improvement.

The findings of this study highlight the importance of organizational factors in shaping nurses' stress levels. Recent systematic reviews have demonstrated that a positive organizational culture, adequate staffing, and supportive

management are associated with lower work-related stress among nurses. These findings support the Job Demands-Resources theory, which has been widely applied in recent nursing research to explain how organizational resources can mitigate stress caused by high job demands

In the present study, many nurses demonstrated strengths in organization, professionalism, and teamwork. Similar findings were reported, who found that experienced nurses are better able to maintain professional performance under stressful conditions.

However, weaknesses were observed in therapeutic communication and patient education. Recent studies indicate that heavy workload and time constraints negatively affect nurses' communication with patients, even when technical performance remains adequate these results suggest that stress may selectively impair interpersonal aspects of nursing care.

The overall job-performance scores indicated that a large proportion of nurses had poor performance levels. This finding is consistent with recent research showing that chronic occupational stress negatively affects nurses' productivity, attention, and quality of.

Between Work-Related Stress and Job Performance

The relationship between work-related stress and job performance observed in this study aligns with recent evidence demonstrating a negative association between stress and performance outcomes among. Even when stress is perceived as manageable, prolonged exposure to high demands may lead to decreased efficiency and compromised patient care.

Recent studies also suggest that individual factors such as emotional intelligence and coping strategies can moderate the impact of stress on job performance. This indicates the importance of both organizational and individual-level interventions to enhance nurse performance.

CONCLUSION

This study was undertaken to assess the level of work-related stress and job performance among nurses working at Civil Hospital Nawabshah and

to explore the relationship between these two important occupational variables. Nursing is widely recognized as a highly demanding profession, particularly in critical care environments where staff must respond to complex patient needs, time pressure, emotional encounters, and heavy workloads. Drawing on a descriptive correlational design and data collected from 187 nurses across intensive care units, operating rooms, emergency departments, and general wards, this study provides valuable insight into the current working conditions of nurses in this setting and contributes to the growing body of evidence from low- and middle-income healthcare contexts.

The demographic profile of the participants revealed a relatively mature and experienced workforce, with a mean age of 41.92 years and most respondents reporting more than six years of clinical experience. The predominance of married nurses and diploma-qualified staff reflects common patterns within public sector hospitals in the region. A large proportion of respondents were employed in high-acuity units such as cardiac ICU, operating theatres, and emergency departments, which are internationally recognized as environments associated with increased psychological and physical demands. These characteristics are important in interpreting the findings, as experience may enhance coping abilities, whereas placement in critical units can intensify occupational stressors.

Findings from the work-related stress questionnaire indicated that nurses experienced substantial job demands, particularly in relation to time pressure, physical workload, and sustained emotional effort. The majority of respondents acknowledged that their jobs required them to work very hard.

Assessment of job performance revealed encouraging strengths as well as notable areas for improvement. The vast majority of nurses demonstrated the ability to organize nursing care effectively, maintain professional behavior during stressful situations, and provide guidance to colleagues. These competencies are likely influenced by the relatively high levels of clinical

experience observed in the sample and reflect a workforce capable of managing technical and procedural demands. Respect for patient dignity and reassurance during stressful procedures were reported at moderate levels, suggesting an overall commitment to ethical and patient-centered care.

REFERENCES

- Ibrahim M, Zakaria A, Abdel-Ghani A. Work Related Stress and Job Performance among Staff Nurses. *Mansoura Nursing Journal*. 2023;10(2):149-60.
- Ahmed MF, Sleem WF, Kassem AH. Effect of working condition and fatigue on performance of staff nurses at Mansoura University Hospital. *Journal of nursing and Health Science*. 2015;4(3):83-91.
- Ella RE, Agharandu AE, Osuchukwu E, Samson-Akpan P. Occupational Stress and Job Performance Among Nurses in a Teaching Hospital, in South-South, Nigeria. *Int J Cur Res Rev* | Vol. 2021;13(11):12.
- Alraimi A, Shelke A. Job stress among nursing staff and its impact on performance in hospitals: a case study. 2023.
- Kumar M, Bhalla P. Stress among nursing staff in hospitals and its relation with job satisfaction, job performance and quality of nursing care: A literature review. *Journal of Nursing and Care*. 2019;8(3):129-36.
- Oketunbi OA, Peter O. Job stress and job performance among academic staff in public universities in Ogun State. *Lagos Education Review*. 2019.
- Chang Y-C, Huang S-T, Wang C-C, Yang C-C. Resilience as a moderator of the effects of types of workplace bullying and job performance. *BMC nursing*. 2025;24(1):254.
- Ilkafah I, Andrianto R, Susanto J, Tyas A, Harisa A. Work stress among nurses in a rural hospital. *Journal of Vocational Nursing*. 2023;4(1):87-92.
- Ari HO. Determining the Relationship Between Work Stress and Job Performance: A Cross-Sectional Study Among Healthcare Workers. *Journal of Nursing Management*. 2025;2025(1):5051149.
- Babapour A-R, Gahassab-Mozaffari N, Fathnezhad-Kazemi A. Nurses' job stress and its impact on quality of life and caring behaviors: a cross-sectional study. *BMC nursing*. 2022;21(1):75.
- Bilal MF, Ali S, Khan F, Ch MK. Impact of Organizational Culture on Safety Performance: Exploring the Mediating Role of Safety Attitudes in Healthcare Sector. *Social Sciences Spectrum*. 2025;4(3):509-31.
- Havaei F, Ma A, Staempfli S, MacPhee M, editors. Nurses' workplace conditions impacting their mental health during COVID-19: A cross-sectional survey study. *Healthcare*; 2021: MDPI.
- Wei N, Zhang X, Liu G, Zhang Y, Li L, Lv X, et al. The mediating effect of sleep quality in the relationship between nocturia and psychosocial functions in nurses: a cross-sectional survey based on TARGET. *BMC nursing*. 2025;24(1):644.
- Babangida AA, Caraballo-Arias Y, Decataldo F, Violante FS. Advancing occupational medicine through wearable technology: A review of sensor systems for biomechanical risk assessment and work-related musculoskeletal disorder prevention. *ACS sensors*. 2025;10(8):5410-32.
- Labrague LJ, Al Sabei S, Al Rawajfah O, AbuAlRub R, Burney I. Interprofessional collaboration as a mediator in the relationship between nurse work environment, patient safety outcomes and job satisfaction among nurses. *Journal of nursing management*. 2022;30(1):268-78.
- Babangida AA, Caraballo-Arias Y, Decataldo F, Violante FS. Advancing occupational medicine through wearable technology: A review of sensor systems for biomechanical risk assessment and work-related musculoskeletal disorder prevention. *ACS sensors*. 2025;10(8):5410-32.

Bilal MF, Ali S, Khan F, Ch MK. Impact of Organizational Culture on Safety Performance: Exploring the Mediating Role of Safety Attitudes in Healthcare Sector. *Social Sciences Spectrum*. 2025;4(3):509-31.

Batool A, Ahmed S, Naveed S, Bilal MA, Khan MA, Nawaz S. The Effect of Leadership Qualities on Organizational Commitment Among Bureaucrats; Emotional Intelligence as a Moderator. *Migration Letters*. 2024;21(S6):146-60.

